

PERFECT HUMAN EDUCATION IN THE PEDAGOGICAL VIEWS OF GREAT FIGURES

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Abstract: the article reflects the views of such great personalities Abu Nasr Farabi, Ibn Sina, Yusuf Has Hajib, M. Ulugbek, A. Navai, Hussein Waiz al-Koshifi, Jalaluddin Dawani, Muslihiddin Saadi Shirozi.

Keywords: education, training, enlightenment, knowledge, morality, manners, perfect person, work, intellectual education, parents, habit, virtue, ability.

Pharoah Describing the image of a knowledgeable, enlightened mature person, he says: "Whoever wants to learn wisdom, let him start from a young age, let him be healthy, have good morals and manners, let him be able to fulfill his word." , be protected from bad deeds, know all the laws and regulations, be knowledgeable and eloquent, respect learned and wise people, do not spare the world of knowledge and people of knowledge, have knowledge about all real material things Let's go." It can be seen from these thoughts that Farabi paid special attention to education and upbringing of young people to become perfect people, especially in intellectual and moral education. the expected goal is not achieved, the child is not mature enough.

Ibn Sina expressed valuable opinions about child education and education methods. Ibn Sina, in his comments on the moral education of the child, also talks about household issues. Raising a child is the main goal and duty of a family parent. A parent who is capable of correcting his own shortcomings can be an educator. One of the most important tools in moral education is to advise the child

in a one-on-one conversation, without touching the child's ego and pride. Ibn Sina considers the formation of moral characteristics in a child in unity with work, physical and mental education as the main factor in making him a human being.

Yusuf Khos Khajib, everyone should grow up worthy of the society. For this, he should receive the necessary education from the day of his birth. When he reflects on the education of Cain girls, he emphasizes to pay attention to their own characteristics. It is necessary to start raising children very early. Only then will they be prevented from engaging in inappropriate behavior.

Mirzo Ulugbek The opinion of the family environment about raising a healthy generation is that, according to allama, the environment in which he is brought up plays an important role in increasing the child's interest in learning. In the family, parents, especially educated parents, should pay special attention to the development of their children as real people.

Alisher Navoi pays special attention to the strength and power of education in the child's growth and development. He believes that as a result of upbringing, the child will grow into a useful and mature person. It is necessary to educate a young child from a very young age. Education helps a person to develop good habits and qualities. He teaches that one of the main factors in growing up is that a person's personality is formed in the relationship with other people, especially as a result of the spiritual and spiritual effects of people on each other.

According to Husayn Vaiz al-Koshifi, it is possible to develop the intellectual ability to re-educate a person through education. According to his pedagogical views, Koshifi pays special attention to the issue of developing children's ability to think independently. Parents demand that teachers pay special attention to this issue. Family and external environment play an important role in this matter. A child should be brought up to be well-behaved, truthful, and faithful to his word.

Jalaluddin Davanithe importance of parents in raising a child was widely discussed. In his opinion, both father and mother have equal rights and equal

participation in family upbringing, helping the child to acquire a certain profession, the rules of good behavior and etiquette are the material basis of acquiring knowledge, science and profession - food, clothes, clothes, necessary items. and must be attractive to supply equipment.

Muslihiddin is one of the great representatives of Eastern classical literature Saadi Shiraz, believes that the family is the foundation for the child's happiness and future. The main support in the family is the father. He is a responsible educator. Saadi According to the pedagogical point of view, a child can be gifted and gifted. Ability does not develop by itself. It is necessary to educate the child for its development, if there is no education, the abilities of the child fade away, education is divided into 3 main ones - intellectual, refined and physical labor education. Adib pays great attention to the task of raising a child to their parents, that is, to family education. Saadi advises parents to start moral education from a young age, taking into account the character of the child, once the character is formed, it does not affect the child.

Kamil Khorazimi, one of the major representatives of the Uzbek social and literary life of the 19th century, promoted the ideas of enlightenment, moral perfection, and patriotism in his works. He describes pedagogical ideas about the importance of science and education in the well-being of people and society, the role of education in the moral maturity of a person, and the unity of moral and intellectual education.

In conclusion, the above pedagogical views of the great figures are important nutrients and theoretical-practical tools for educating the young generation morally, intellectually, and spiritually.

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